

RISK FACTORS FOR KNEE OSTEOARTHRITIS

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ABSTRACT

The main purpose of this article is to highlight the role of risk factors for knee osteoarthritis in the development of the disease. Thanks to the article, all doctors can learn in detail about risk factors and eliminate or prevent risk factors for osteoarthritis diseases.

Keywords: osteoarthritis, osteoarthritis, OA, knee joint, radiography, X-ray joint space, ultrasound.

INTRODUCTION

Osteoarthritis (OA) is a heterogeneous group of diseases of various etiologies, but with similar biological, morphological and clinical manifestations and outcome, which are based on the defeat of all components of the joint, rimirly cartilage, as well as subchondral bone, synovium, ligaments, capsule and periarticular muscles. So, in the Neolithic the period of OA of the joints reached, according to excavations, 20% (maybe the reasons were being in the dark and damp caves, scarcity and monotony of food, unfavorable climate) Ancient medicine often had to deal with OA. In his work *On the Joints*, Hippocrates discusses it along with gout and other diseases of the joints. The English doctor W. Heberden described the nodules, called him name and considered as one of the manifestations of OA. In the second half of the 19th century, a French clinician J. M. Charcot singled out OA and rheumatoid arthritis from among rheumatic diseases and considered them as the main variants of one pathological process-deforming arthritis. In 1904 an American orthopedist R. Osgood, based on x-ray studies, coined the term atrophic arthritis. However, an independent nosological form of OA was officially recognized only in 1911, when at the International Congress of Physicians in London it was proposed to divide all

diseases of the joints into primary inflammatory and primary degenerative. OA — multifactorial chronic progressive joint disease that develops as a result of mechanical and biological causes that destabilize articular cartilage and subchondral bone normal relationship between degradation and synthesis of components matrix by chondrocytes. In foreign literature, instead of term "osteoarthritis", the more adequate term "osteoarthritis" is often used, emphasizing the important role inflammatory component in development and progression diseases.

As you know, the cardinal symptom of osteoarthritis, regardless of the stage of this disease, is joint pain. Persistent arthralgia reflects a persistent inflammatory process and inadequate repair of joint structures, which determines reduced tolerance to mechanical stress and progressive biomechanical disturbances. Therefore, long-lasting unpleasant sensations in the joint area (not only pain, but and a feeling of stiffness, stiffness, instability) should cause alertness in terms of the possibility of developing early osteoarthritis. In this regard, a number of studies have been undertaken with an attempt to combine clinical manifestations with the data of instrumental studies.

MAIN PART

What are the risk factors?

Risk factors include the following:

- genetic - female gender, type II collagen gene defects, congenital bone disease and joints;
- acquired - old age, overweight, estrogen deficiency in postmenopausal women, acquired diseases of bones and joints, operations on the joints (for example, meniscectomy);
- environmental factors - excessive load on joints, joint injuries, etc.

Radiography still plays a major role in the diagnosis of OA of the knee joint. This is due to the availability of this method, simplicity of research, cost-effectiveness and established well-known criteria diagnostics . Along with the traditional method of radiography of the knee joint - the study of the knee joint in standard projections when the patient is in a horizontal position, there is a well-

known method of radiographic examination in a vertical position in the posterior-anterior projection with a slight flexion of the knee joint. It is believed that in this position the central X-ray beam is directed along tangent to the plane of the tibial condyles and the articular space (X-ray joint space) . Another method that can be used to examine the knee joint is ultrasonography (ultrasound).

To date, ultrasound of the knee joints is generally recognized nano and taking into account the advantages (lack of radiation loads, accessibility, non-invasiveness, real-time imaging, relatively low cost of research), the method is increasingly used in the diagnosis of diseases and injuries of the knee joint, including including for the diagnosis of OA. Last The international system Outcome Measures in Rheumatology for Arthritis Clinical Trail (OMERACT) is gaining more and more popularity. Studies of the knee joints, the essence of which is a scoring assessment of pathological changes, primarily inflammatory. scoring a score (0–3) is used to evaluate thickening synovial membrane in synovitis, the level of expression of Doppler signals in the synovial shell and accumulation of free fluid in the articular cavity . The principle of integrated Evaluation of individual structures of the knee joint makes it possible to increase objectivity and improve the quality of diagnostics.

Clinical signs and symptoms

OA is manifested by severe pain and deformity joints, leading to a violation of their functions. More often in total, load joints (knee, hip), small joints of the hands (distal and proximal interphalangeal joints of the hands, the first metacarpal joint of the hand) and spine. Most of great clinical importance is the defeat of the hip and knee joints, which is the main cause decrease in the quality of life and disability in osteoarthritis. In contrast to inflammatory diseases of the joints extra-articular manifestations in OA are not observed.

Examination methods

Examination of the joint can reveal changes in its appearance, due to the development of a pathological process in it. Performed in standing, sitting and lying down to identify the shape of the joint, swelling, smoothing of the contours and hyperemia of the joint area, the absence normal folds over joints (e.g.,

interphalangeal), muscle atrophy, asymmetry or malformation of joint boundaries, intra-articular effusion, pathological position of the limb, defiguration, deformity and contracture, gait, lameness, excessive mobility. Palpation reveals crepitus and crunch in the joint, sometimes - the presence of free bodies in the knee or elbow joints, the so-called "articular mice", joint tenderness, free fluid in the joint with synovitis, the condition of the ligamentous apparatus (in the knee - external, internal, cruciform ligaments), tone of periarticular muscles. Study volume and the quality of active and passive movements in the joints. Active commits the patient himself arbitrarily. Passive in the joint under study is done by a doctor with full muscle relaxation of the patient. With both types of movements it is possible to most fully reveal all the reserves of motor joint functions.

Important in the diagnosis of OA measurement (comparison) limb lengths. It can reveal the shortening of one of them (on the affected side).

In recent years, a number of special methods have been developed that make it possible to refine and visualize the structure the affected joint. These include ultrasonic joint scanning (sonography), arthroscopy, magnetic resonance imaging (MRI).

Among the non-invasive methods for diagnosing OA, the leading sonography takes the place in terms of informativeness. Unlike from most methods of examining tissues of the musculoskeletal system (radiography, computer tomography) it is not related to radiation exposure and can be carried out multiple times. This allows you to use this method is not only for diagnosing diseases joints, but also to assess the effectiveness of ongoing therapeutic measures. It helps to determine articular cartilage thickness, which is important in diagnosis of OA, even a slight accumulation of fluid in joint (hemarthrosis, synovitis), rupture of the meniscus and ligamentous apparatus, localization and size of the "articular mouse", as well as osteophytes and hypertrophied synovial folds, degenerative changes in intra-articular and periarticular structures.

Diagnosis and recommended investigations

For primary (idiopathic) osteoarthritis, changes in standard laboratory parameters are not typical. In elderly patients, who make up the majority of patients with OA, a slight increase in ESR and RF titers may be related to age factors and does not exclude the diagnosis of osteoarthritis. When researching synovial fluid reveals a slight turbidity, an increase in viscosity; the number of leukocytes - less than 2000/mm³, neutrophils - less than 25%.

According to the clinical and radiological picture, different authors distinguish 4 stages of the disease. But there is no strict relationship between clinical and radiological signs in the early stages. Severe pain and limited mobility are often noted with minor radiological changes in the joint.

General principles of treatment

Treatment of osteoarthritis remains mainly symptomatic, using oral, intra-articular and local drugs and is aimed at achieving the following goals:

- slowing down the progression of the disease;
- reducing pain and inflammation;
- reducing the risk of exacerbations and damage to new joints;
- improving the quality of life;
- prevention of disability.

To suppress pain, use a wide complex non-pharmacological (physiotherapy, physiotherapy, patient education) and pharmacological methods. None of these methods is universal. When choosing a treatment method for a particular patient should take into account the characteristics of the course of the disease - severity of symptoms, rate of progression diseases, the presence of an inflammatory component; individual characteristics of the patient - age, the presence of concomitant diseases, their nature and pharmacotherapy ;properties of medicines.

Non-pharmacological treatments

Mechanical unloading of the joint is a determining factor both in reducing the pain syndrome and and in the treatment of OA in general. This includes recommendations for the exclusion of a long stay in a fixed posture, standing for a long time, walking for a long time, repetitive stereotypical movements, carrying

heavy loads leading to mechanical overload of certain areas joints. In advanced stages of the disease, the patient It is useful to walk with a cane, crutches. When expressed pain in the exacerbation phase can be assigned semi-bed rest. Clear pathogenetic recommendations on the OA diet currently does not exist. important a condition in the treatment of OA of the knee joints is the reduction of excess body weight.

Widely used for rehabilitation treatment OA physiotherapy methods reduce the pain syndrome, as well as inflammation and muscle spasm, improve microcirculation, have a beneficial effect on metabolic processes in the tissues of the joint. Wherein using ultraviolet light, electrical currents, alternating magnetic fields, electrophoresis and phonophoresis of drugs on the joint.

Pharmacotherapy

According to the modern classification, antiarthrotic drugs are divided into three groups:

- 1) symptomatic fast-acting drugs (simple analgesics and NSAIDs);
- 2) symptomatic slow-acting drugs or drugs that modify symptoms (chondroitin sulfate, glucosamine sulfate, hyaluronic acid preparations);
- 3) drugs that modify the structure of the cartilage (possibly chondroitin sulfate has such an effect, glucosamine sulfate).

In addition, in some patients with erosive osteoarthritis or frequent exacerbations of synovitis, long-term treatment with hydroxychloroquine and colchicine is reasonable.

Surgery

Extremely effective surgical treatment (arthroscopic surgery and joint arthroplasty), which, however, should only be performed when severe disabling lesion of the knee and hip joints, accompanied by severe pain. Used in the treatment of coxarthrosis and gonarthrosis:

- varieties of arthroplasty for alignment of articular surfaces, temporarily providing them congruence, with opening of the subchondral bone for fibroblasts

and stem cells to enter the joint cavity, giving rise to the formation of fibrous cartilage, and with the opening of access to the source of cartilage differon;

- mosaic plasty used to close small (up to 4 cm) monolayer effects cartilage - the consequences of its traumatic injury;
- arthrodesis;
- tenotomy - dissection of the tendon in order to restore the disturbed balance of the muscles or elimination of contracture;
- osteocryoanalgesia - a method of surgical treatment pain syndrome in OA, which consists in toning and cryodestruction of the subtrochanteric region femur;
- endoprosthesis replacement is the most radical method treatment of OA using metal-polymer or ceramic endoprostheses that take into account the biomechanics of the joints.

All modern endoprostheses are divided into two large groups – cemented and cementless fixation. Indications for the use of cementless endoprostheses are the young age of patients (under 50–60 years), good bone base, conical shape of the medullary canal of the femur.

Cemented endoprostheses are used in patients older than 65–70 years, as well as in the presence of signs osteoporosis and wide medullary cavity. Endoprosthetics occupies the main place in the surgery of this pathology, and up to 80% of all operations constitutes a hip replacement.

CONCLUSION

1. The most common clinical manifestation OA was an increase in pain during exercise (55.88%) and duration of clinical manifestations more than 12 months (50.0%).
2. The most significant radiation signs were obtained in patients with various stages of knee OA (<0.001) with clinical picture of the disease, namely the presence of effusion in the joint cavity, the presence of osteophytes and degenerative changes in the medial meniscus.

3. A High Strength Correlation Has Been Found between the level of pain according to VAS and the stage of OA, the volume of effusion, the size of osteophytes; moderate strength - with the thickness of the cartilage of the medial condyle thigh, thick patellofemoral cartilage articulation, degenerative changes in the medial and lateral menisci, the presence of and size of Baker's cysts.
4. High and medium correlations strength of clinical manifestations and changes in ray data include rhinestone several features, none of the features is decisive.

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